

Across

1. Dutch scientist who lived in delft and invented the microscope

2. A Italian free mind; with his telescope, he was the first to see the craters of the Moon

3. Italian priest, he discovered the diffraction of light (no connection with the Prince of Monaco)

4. Indian researcher that give his name to an important spectroscopy technique

5. Austrian physicist, he explain the color of binary stars using his "effect"

Down

1. Iraqi philosopher and physicist, he wrote the first book on Optics in 1015 and postulate that the speed of light is finite.

2. Dutch inventor of the pendulum clock, he is more remembered for his wave theory of light

3. English polymath, he improved the microscope and coined the term cell

4. English polymath, he is known for his holes

5. Ancient Greek, known for plenty, he postulated that light travels in straight line.

6. German Astronomer, he wrote the laws of planetary motion

7. American engineer, he built the first laser in 1960

8. Scottish physicist, known for his 4 equations, demonstrate that white what made of 3 colors.

9. American engineer, he conceived the first incandescent lamp

Light Scientist

Solutions

Across

1. Anton van Leeuwenhoek

2. Galileo Galilei

3. Francesco Maria Grimaldi

4. Sir Chandrasekhara Raman

5. Christian Doppler

Down

1. Abū 'Alī al-Ḥasan ibn al-Ḥaytham, known by the Latinization Alhazen or Alhacen

2. Christiaan Huygens

3. Robert Hooke

4. Thomas Young

5. Aristoteles

6. Johannes Kepler

7. Theodore Harold Maiman

8. James Clerk Maxwell

9. Thomas Edison

